

New Fragmentation Pathways in the EIMS of 4-Methylcoumarins Useful in their Identification

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The mass spectra of 35 differently substituted 4-methylcoumarins have been studied in detail, and it was observed that the fragmentation pathways of the coumarins having dihydroxy, dimethoxy and diacetoxy substitution pattern in the aromatic ring are different from those having mono-oxygenation pattern in this ring. Similarly, the mass spectra of 4-methylcoumarins not having an alkyl side chain at the C-3 position was found different from those having such an alkyl side chain at the C-3 position. These new fragmentation pathways could be of great help in the structure elucidation of new/natural 4-methylcoumarins.

4-Methylcoumarins are an important group of recently discovered natural products; quite a few of them have been found to possess choleric¹, analgesic², antispermatic³ and diuretic⁴ properties. It has been observed¹ that coumarins carrying a 4-methyl function have much stronger choleric property than those lacking this functionality; furthermore, the metabolites of the former compounds were rapidly excreted while those of the latter compounds slowly excreted. A 4-methylcoumarin having a 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)methyl side chain has recently been isolated from a natural source⁵. Except for two reports^{6,7} of the fragmentation pattern of only a few 4-methylcoumarins, no detailed and systematic study of the mass fragmentation pathways of this important class of compounds has been carried out so far. In view of their natural occurrence and their better *in vivo* properties as medicinal agents, we report the fragmentation pathways in the electron impact mass spectra of 35 differently substituted 4-methylcoumarins which can help in the structure elucidation of new/natural compounds of this group.

- 1, R=H, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OH, R₄=H
- 2, R=H, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 3, R=H, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCOCH₃, R₄=H
- 4, R=H, R₁=OH, R₂=H, R₃=OH, R₄=H
- 5, R=H, R₁=OCH₃, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 6, R=H, R₁=OCOCH₃, R₂=H, R₃=OCOCH₃, R₄=H
- 7, R=H, R₁=H, R₂=OH, R₃=OH, R₄=H
- 8, R=H, R₁=H, R₂=OCH₃, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 9, R=H, R₁=H, R₂=OCOCH₃, R₃=OCOCH₃, R₄=H
- 10, R=H, R₁=H, R₂=OH, R₃=OH, R₄=OH
- 11, R=H, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=OCH₃
- 12, R=H, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCOCH₃, R₄=OCOCH₃
- 13, R=CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OH, R₄=H
- 14, R=CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 15, R=CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCOCH₃, R₄=H
- 16, R=CH₂COOEt, R₁=OH, R₂=H, R₃=OH, R₄=H
- 17, R=CH₂COOEt, R₁=OCH₃, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 18, R=CH₂COOEt, R₁=OCOCH₃, R₂=H, R₃=OCOCH₃, R₄=H
- 19, R=CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=OH, R₃=OH, R₄=H
- 20, R=CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=OCH₃, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 21, R=CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=OCOCH₃, R₃=OCOCH₃, R₄=H
- 22, R=CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OH, R₄=OH
- 23, R=CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=OCH₃
- 24, R=CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCOCH₃, R₄=OCOCH₃
- 25, R=CH₂CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OH, R₄=H
- 26, R=CH₂CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 27, R=CH₂CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCOCH₃, R₄=H
- 28, R=CH₂CH₂COOEt, R₁=OH, R₂=H, R₃=OH, R₄=H
- 29, R=CH₂CH₂COOEt, R₁=OCH₃, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 30, R=CH₂CH₂COOEt, R₁=OCOCH₃, R₂=H, R₃=OCOCH₃, R₄=H
- 31, R=CH₂CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=OH, R₃=OH, R₄=H
- 32, R=CH₂CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=OCH₃, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 33, R=CH₂CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OH, R₄=OH
- 34, R=CH₂CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=OCH₃
- 35, R=CH₂CH₂COOEt, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCOCH₃, R₄=OCOCH₃

Experimental

The 4-methylcoumarins (1-35) used in the present study were synthesised via Pechman condensation of the corresponding phenol and ester, and their methyl ethers and acetates were prepared by standard procedures using dimethyl sulphate/ K_2CO_3 in acetone and pyridine/acetic anhydride, respectively. All the compounds were purified by chromatographic techniques (tlc and cc) and recrystallisation and the purity was $\geq 99\%$. The EIMS of different samples were recorded between 120 and 200°.

Results and Discussion

The prominent fragments seen in the EIMS of compounds 1-35 are shown in Tables 1-3. For the

purpose of discussion, these 35 compounds have been divided into three categories depending upon

the substituent present at the C-3 position. As shown in Table 1, compounds 1 and 2 exhibit identical fragmentation pattern to those described earlier^{6,7} for these compounds. Compounds 4, 7 and 10 show the base peak molecular ion at m/z 192; important and prominent fragments observed in these three compounds were found to be similar. In all these compounds, first there is a loss of a CO

TABLE 1—PROMINENT AND IMPORTANT MASS FRAGMENTS IN THE MASS SPECTRA OF 4-METHYLCOUMARINS NOT HAVING ANY SUBSTITUENT AT THE C-3 POSITION

Compd. no.	Mol. weight	m/z (rel. int. %)
1	176	176(100), 148(79), 147(50), 119(7.9), 91(15.1).
2	190	190(100), 162(82.4), 147(78.4), 119(5.9), 91(3.5).
3	218	218(16.9), 176(100), 148(57.1), 147(13.4), 119(2.5), 91(6.9).
4	192	192(100), 164(78), 163(33.1), 147(3.1), 136(3.6), 135(6.9), 121(7.6), 107(4.7).
5	220	220(100), 192(99.2), 177(66.2), 149(16.1), 134(5.9), 121(6.4), 106(8.6), 77(13.1).
6	276	276(10.9), 234(93.1), 192(100), 164(28.6), 163(5.1).
7	192	192(100), 164(71), 163(54.2), 147(3), 136(7.7), 135(4.1), 121(1.5), 107(2.3).
8	220	220(100), 205(27.1), 192(18.8), 177(25.2), 149(6.8), 134(4.6), 121(10.4), 106(4.7).
9	276	276(8), 234(16.1), 192(100), 164(17.8), 163(5.8).
10	192	192(100), 164(60.3), 163(35.8), 147(3.4), 136(7.8), 135(4.5), 121(7.6), 107(3.9).
11	220	220(100), 205(19.4), 192(14.4), 177(32.9), 149(5.9), 134(3.1), 121(5.9), 106(11.8), 77(6.6).
12	276	276(4.8), 234(11.1), 192(100), 164(73.5), 163(4.3).

molecule to give the radical ion at m/z 164 and then gives four different fragments—two fragments at m/z 163 obtained due to the loss of a hydrogen radical, one fragment at m/z 136 by further loss of a CO molecule and the fourth at m/z 147 due to the loss of a OH radical. The fragment at m/z 135 is due to the loss of CO molecule from the ion at m/z 163 which further loses either a CH_3 radical to give the fragment at m/z 121 or a CO molecule to give the ion at m/z 107 (Scheme 1).

Compounds 5, 8 and 11, having dimethoxy substitution pattern in the aromatic ring, give the base peak molecular ion at m/z 220. The fragmentation pattern of these three compounds were found similar and are as depicted in Scheme 2. There are two possible pathways; in the pathway I, the molecular ion peak first loses a CH_3 radical which is followed by the loss of a CO molecule giving the ions at m/z 205 and 177, which may also be obtained in pathway II by the loss of a CO molecule, followed by the loss of a CH_3 radical from the molecular ion peak. The ion at m/z 177 may further lose a CO molecule giving another stable ion at m/z 149, which further loses a CO molecule to give another

fragment at m/z 121, else it may lose a CH_3 radical to give the fragment at m/z 134 which further loses in succession one molecule each of CO and CHO to give the ion at m/z 77 (Scheme 2).

The peak at m/z 205 is seen only in compounds 8 and 11 and not in compound 5 because the $(M-15)^+$ fragments, (a) and (b) found in case of compounds 8 and 11, respectively, would be stable (as they are *o*- and *p*-quinonoid) and would be formed readily. On the other hand, the $(M-15)^+$ fragment (c) formed from compound 5 would not be stable (as it is *m*-quinonoid), hence it is not seen. Thus the appearance of a $(M-\text{CH}_3)^+$ peak in the EIMS of 4-methylcoumarin would indicate the presence of a OCH_3 group at either position C-6 or C-8 and can be used in distinguishing these two methoxyl groups from those present at C-5 or C-7 positions.

Compounds 6, 9 and 12 having two acetoxy groups in the aromatic ring show the molecular ion peak at m/z 276; in these compounds first there is a loss of two units of ketene ($-\text{CH}_3\text{CO}$) to give the base peak ion at m/z 192, which was found identical with compounds 4, 7 and 10 and the further fragmentation pathways were same as in compounds 4, 7 and 10 (Scheme 1). The molecular ion peak in compound 13 appeared at m/z 252; the peak at m/z 147 may be due to two fragments obtained via two different pathways as shown in Scheme 3. In the pathway I, first there is a loss of a $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{O}$ radical to give an ion at m/z 217; it further loses

Scheme 2

a CO molecule in two different ways, giving two different ions at *m/z* 189, both of which can lose a CO molecule to give the ion at *m/z* 161, which loses a CH₂ radical to form the stable ion at *m/z* 147. In the pathway II, first there is a loss of a CH₂CH₂OH molecule giving the fragment at *m/z* 216, which then loses a CO molecule to give the radical ion at *m/z* 188, followed by the loss of CHCO radical to form the ion at *m/z* 147 (Scheme 3). Similar to compound 13, 14 also exhibited two fragmentation pathways in its mass spectrum. In the pathway I, first there is a loss of CH₂CH₂O radical to give the ion at *m/z* 231. This further loses a CO molecule to give two different base peak fragments at *m/z* 203, which further lose a CO molecule followed by the CH₂ radical and CO molecule, giving a radical ion at *m/z* 132. In the

Scheme 3

pathway II, first there is a loss of CH₂CH₂OH molecule to give the fragment at *m/z* 230, which on sequential loss of a CO molecule and CHCO radical gives the ion at *m/z* 161 (Scheme 4). As shown in

Scheme 4

Table 2, compound 15 exhibits the molecular ion peak at m/z 304 which loses a ketene molecule to give the fragment at m/z 262. This fragment at m/z 262 was found identical with the molecular ion peak of compound 13. Further fragmentation pattern is as in compound 13 (Scheme 3).

TABLE 2—PROMINENT AND IMPORTANT MASS FRAGMENTS IN THE MASS SPECTRA OF 4-METHYLCOUMARINS HAVING AN (ETHOXYCARBONYLMETHYL) SIDECHAIN AT THE C-3 POSITION

Compd. no.	Mol. weight	m/z (rel. int. %)
13	262	262(28.4), 217(13.1), 216(30.3), 190(16.4), 189(100), 188(13.3), 161(13.6), 147(2.5).
14	276	276(15.2), 231(7.4), 230(16.4), 204(19), 203(100), 202(8.6), 175(11.3), 161(3.8), 160(3.3), 132(4.7).
15	304	304(13.5), 262(53.1), 259(8.5), 217(5.9), 216(38.7), 190(17.9), 189(100), 188(15.7), 161(9.3), 147(1.3).
16	278	278(19.2), 233(11), 232(31.5), 206(13.5), 205(100), 204(19.7), 177(13.5), 163(3.6).
17	306	306(24.6), 261(5.6), 260(11), 234(14.5), 233(100), 232(5.1), 217(4.5), 205(6.5), 189(3.8), 175(3.1).
18	362	362(11.3), 320(42.8), 317(9.7), 278(50.3), 274(22.7), 233(9.6), 232(68.6), 206(12.4), 205(32.4), 204(64), 177(8.2).
19	278	278(41.3), 233(11.3), 232(19), 206(16.2), 205(100), 204(13.2), 177(21.7), 163(2.3).
20	306	306(51.7), 261(7.5), 260(8.6), 234(16.8), 233(100), 232(6.8), 217(2.3), 205(12.2), 189(3).
21	362	362(7), 320(19.4), 317(6.1), 278(100), 233(5.7), 232(33.6), 206(14), 205(64.5), 204(18.4), 192(44.5), 177(9.6).
22	278	278(3.5), 233(9.7), 232(18.4), 206(15.4), 205(100), 204(12.4), 177(13.3), 163(2.5).
23	306	306(19.3), 261(7.9), 260(13), 234(15.9), 233(100), 232(9.2), 217(1.5), 205(5.3), 189(3.7), 175(2.7).
24	362	362(7.3), 320(14.8), 317(7.3), 278(100), 233(8.6), 232(64.4), 206(9.3), 205(52.2), 204(39.2), 177(5.7).

Compounds 16, 19 and 22 showed the molecular ion peak at m/z 278 as shown in Table 2. The fragmentation pattern in all the three compounds was found similar to that of compound 13. There are two possible pathways in the mass spectrum of these compounds. In the first pathway, first there is a loss of a $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{O}$ radical to give the ion at m/z 233. The fragment which forms the base peak at m/z 205 may be due to two ions formed by the loss of CO molecule in two different ways from this ion. The fragments at m/z 205 lose a CO molecule to give the ion at m/z 177, which as a result of emission of a CH_3 radical gives the ion at m/z 163. In the second pathway, first there is a loss of a $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ molecule to give the radical ion at m/z 232, which on sequential loss of a CO

molecule and CHCO radical gives another ion at m/z 163 (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5

Compounds 17, 20 and 23 showed their molecular ion peaks at m/z 306. All these three compounds exhibited similar type of fragments as shown in Table 2. In these compounds also there are two possible pathways; in pathway I, first there is a loss of a $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{O}$ radical to give the ion at m/z 261, which is followed by the loss of a CO molecule in two different ways giving the base peak ions at m/z 233. These ions now lose another molecule of CO resulting in the formation of the ion at m/z 205. In the pathway II, first there is a loss of a $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ molecule from the molecular ion peak giving a radical ion at m/z 260, followed by the loss of a CO molecule and CH_3 radical to give the ion at m/z 217, which after losing a CO molecule gives another ion at m/z 189, followed by the loss of a CH_3 radical to give the ion at m/z 175 (Scheme 6).

Compounds 18, 21 and 24 exhibit the molecular ion peak at m/z 362 and the fragmentation pattern in these three compounds was found similar, as shown in Table 2. These compounds first lose a ketene molecule giving a radical ion at m/z 320, which is followed by the loss of another ketene molecule to give the fragment at m/z 278. This fragment was found identical with the molecular ion peaks of compounds 16, 19 and 22, respectively, and the further fragmentation pattern in these compounds was found similar to those of compounds

Scheme 6

16, 19 and **22** as shown in Scheme 5. In these compounds another fragment obtained at m/z 317 is due to the loss of a CH_3CH_2O radical from the molecular ion peak; in compound **16** the fragment obtained at m/z 274 is due to the loss of a CH_3CH_2OH molecule from the fragment at m/z 320 (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7

Compound **25** exhibits an intense molecular ion peak at m/z 276. There are two possible pathways in the mass spectrum of this compound having 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)ethyl side chain as in compounds having 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)methyl side chain. In the pathway I, the ion obtained at m/z 231 by the loss of a CH_3CH_2O radical from the molecular ion peak fragments further in three different ways to give the base peak radical ion at m/z 202 by the loss of a CHO molecule, the ion at m/z 203 by the

loss of a CO molecule and another ion at m/z 189 by the loss of a CH_3CO molecule, respectively. The ions at m/z 203 and 189 may lose a CH_3CO molecule and CO molecule, respectively, to give the ion at m/z 161. The radical ion at m/z 202 loses a CO molecule resulting in the formation of the fragment at m/z 174. In the pathway II, the molecular ion peak may lose a CH_3CH_2OH molecule to give the radical ion at m/z 230 which can lose either a CHCO radical to give the ion at m/z 189 or it may lose a CO molecule which is followed by the loss of a CHCO radical resulting in the formation of the same ion at m/z 161 as in pathway I; this ion may lose a CH_3 radical to give another ion at m/z 147 (Scheme 8). Compound **26** exhibits the

Scheme 8

molecular ion peak at m/z 290; similar to compound **25**, this compound also shows two pathways in its mass spectrum (Scheme 9).

Compound **27** shows the molecular ion peak at m/z 318. It undergoes fragmentation in two different ways. In the pathway I, it first loses a ketene molecule resulting in the formation of the radical ion at m/z 276, which was found identical with the molecular ion peak of compound **25** and the further fragmentation pattern is similar to that of compound **25**. In the second pathway, first it loses a CH_3CH_2O radical without losing the ketene molecule from the molecular ion peak giving the ion at m/z 273, which is followed by the loses of CO and CH_3CO molecules in different orders to give fragments at m/z 203, 245 and 231. The fragment at m/z 273 may also lose a CHO radical to give the fragment at m/z 244. In still another manner, the molecular ion loses a CH_3CH_2OH

Scheme 9

molecule resulting in the formation of the fragment at m/z 272, which is followed by the loss of a CO molecule and CHCO radical to give the ion at m/z 203 (Scheme 10).

Scheme 10

The mass spectrum of compounds 28, 31 and 33 exhibited similar peaks (Table 3); the molecular

TABLE 3—PROMINENT AND IMPORTANT MASS FRAGMENTS IN THE MASS SPECTRA OF 4-METHYLCOUMARINS HAVING (ETHOXYCARBONYL)ETHYL SIDECHAIN AT C-3 POSITION

Compd. no.	Mol. weight	m/z (rel. int. %)
25	276	276(22.8), 231(9.3), 230(18.4), 203(31.5), 202(100), 201(11.5), 189(22.7), 174(9.6), 161(5.8), 147(2.3).
26	290	290(14.6), 245(17), 244(7), 217(23.5), 216(100), 215(12.5), 203(40.3), 188(9.1), 175(8.8).
27	318	318(11.6), 276(7.8), 273(15), 272(11.8), 245(5.2), 244(13.6), 231(7.6), 230(16.7), 216(15.2), 203(28.1), 202(100), 201(12.8), 189(20.4), 174(6), 161(4.8), 147(1.8).
28	292	292(19.6), 247(23.1), 246(11.5), 219(23), 218(100), 217(24), 205(47), 190(14), 177(10), 163(3.1).
29	320	320(32.3), 275(16.8), 247(20), 246(100), 245(6), 233(6.2), 218(9.8), 205(8.7).
30	376	376(13.3), 334(24.2), 331(16.3), 302(9.8), 292(12.4), 289(9.5), 288(25.2), 260(31.7), 246(37.6), 245(12.2), 219(22.1), 218(100), 217(11.6), 205(20.4), 190(5.5), 177(4.8).
31	292	292(21.1), 247(22), 246(11), 219(23.9), 218(100), 217(23.8), 205(36.3), 190(11.1), 177(12.6), 163(2.7).
32	320	320(40.4), 275(10.1), 247(27.8), 246(100), 245(8.2), 233(40.8), 218(5.2), 205(10.5).
33	292	292(22.2), 247(19.8), 246(6.9), 219(21.4), 218(100), 217(15.8), 205(36.5), 190(9.7), 177(8.5), 163(1.8).
34	320	320(0.5), 275(1.2), 247(19.8), 246(6.9), 245(1.3), 233(4.6), 218(1.1), 205(0.5).
35	376	376(10.4), 334(13.5), 331(14.2), 292(81.3), 247(15.1), 246(82.1), 219(20.4), 218(100), 217(10.8), 205(17), 190(4.4), 177(4.4).

ion peak in these three compounds appeared at m/z 292, which undergoes fragmentation in two different pathways. In the pathway I, the molecular ion loses $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}$ radical giving the ion at m/z 247, which then loses a CHO radical forming the base peak radical ion at m/z 218; it then loses a CO molecule resulting in the formation of a fragment at m/z 190. The ion at m/z 247 may also lose a CO molecule and CH_2CO molecule in different orders to give the ions at m/z 219, 205 and 177, which then loses a CH_2 radical giving the ion at m/z 163. In the pathway II, the molecular ion loses a $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ molecule to give the radical ion at m/z 246 which loses a CO molecule, followed by a CHCO or H radical to give the fragments at m/z 218, 177 and 217 (Scheme 11).

The molecular ion peaks in compounds 29, 32 and 34 appeared at m/z 320 and the different fragments in these compounds were found similar (Table 3). In these three compounds, the molecular ion first loses a $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}$ radical forming the ion at m/z 275, which fragments in three different pathways as in other compounds. In the first pathway, this ion loses a CHO radical resulting

chain at the C-3 position is much different from those of the compounds lacking this functionality. Such substituent increases the stability of the fragments and fragmentations below m/z 160 are usually not seen. These are new fragmentation pathways and could be of much help in discerning the presence of such alkyl substituents in this important class of compounds.

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